

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project “Into-DIALOGUE”

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Maps with selected parameters characterizing EU and Turkish agrarian landscapes

Presentation of the results of the farms characteristics

Indicators for the characterization of the attributes that can affect the application of soil-based agroecological measures

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Explanation of lists' numbering

The figures and tables under both lists, are numbered according to the Chapter they are in. This means that for example, the second table of Chapter 3 is named Table 3.2. This method aims to improve readability and clarity when looking for specific figures/tables.

GLOSSARY

Throughout the text, there are multiple terms used according to the definition given by Eurostat. Here they are listed and explained (Eurostat's Glossary).

Agricultural holding, or **holding** or **farm** is a single unit, both technically and economically, operating under a single management and which undertakes economic activities in agriculture within the economic territory of the European Union, either as its primary or secondary activity. The holding may also provide other supplementary (non-agricultural) products and services. For the full definition, check:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Agricultural_holding

Holder of the agricultural holding (also called **farm owner** through the text) is the natural person, group of natural persons or legal person on whose account and in whose name the holding is operated and who is legally and economically responsible for the holding, i.e. who takes the economic risks of the holding. The holder can own the holding outright or rent it or be a hereditary long-term leaseholder or a usufructuary or a trustee. The holder may have delegated to a manager all or part of the power of the decision-making regarding the normal daily financial and production routines of the holding. In such cases it is said to be "holder/not manager". In the cases where the holder is also the manager it is said to be "holder/manager". Holder who is a natural person and the sole holder of an independent holding is generally, but not necessarily, also the manager. On the group holdings, only the main holder (one person) is accounted.

Manager of the agricultural holding is the person responsible for the normal financial and production routines of running the holding. The holder of the agricultural holding is, in most cases, also the manager. In this case the term holder-manager applies. However, if the holder is not the manager, they pass the responsibility of managing the holding to someone else, for example a member of the family, maybe a spouse, or a person with no family ties to the holder. In such cases the manager undertakes the day-to-day management of the holding without assumption of economic and legal responsibility for it (as these are the responsibilities of the holder). Holdings can have: (1) only one manager, or (2) co-managers in the case where the holder shares the management with a spouse or family member.

Utilised agricultural area (UAA), is the total area taken up by arable land, permanent grassland, permanent crops, and kitchen gardens used by the holding, regardless of the type of tenure or whether it is used as a part of common land. It includes arable land, permanent grassland, permanent crops, and kitchen gardens, but excluding mushrooms, unutilised agricultural area, woodland, other land occupied by buildings, farmyards, tracks, ponds, utilised agricultural area which is a property of the owner but is leased or rented to someone else, and common land which is not used.

Arable land: land worked (ploughed or tilled) regularly, generally under a system of crop rotation. This includes cereals, dry pulses and protein crops, root crops, industrial crops, plants harvested green, fresh vegetables (including melons), strawberries, flowers and ornamental plants, seeds and seedlings, other arable land crops, and fallow land. It excludes berries plantations even if their permanence on the plot is less than 5 years, land that has been definitely taken out of cultivation even if less than 5 years have passed since it was last cropped, and cultivated mushrooms.

Tillage practices refer to the tillage operations carried out between the harvest and following sowing/cultivation operation. Tillage, crop rotation and soil cover are practices related to pesticide and nutrient runoff, soil erosion, soil compaction etc. The information about tillage practices helps assess other indicators as such on soil cover, risks of nitrate leaching, and organic matter of soils. Any disturbance of soils may enhance turnover of nutrients and thereby increase the potential risk

of loss of, for example, nitrogenous compounds and phosphorus through surface runoff and soil erosion. Especially, tillage in the autumn may increase the potential risk of losses during the following winter period. The different tillage practices distinguished are conservation tillage, conventional tillage, and zero tillage.

Conservational tillage refers to the arable land treated by conservation (low) tillage, which is a tillage practice or system of practices that leaves plant residues (at least 30 %) on the soil surface for erosion control and moisture conservation, normally by not inverting the soil. Conservation tillage can include the following systems:

- Strip tillage or zonal tillage refers to a system where strips 5 to 20 cm in width are prepared to receive the seed whilst the soil along the intervening bands is not disturbed and remains covered with residues. The system causes more soil disturbance and provides less cover along the rows than zero tillage.
- Tined tillage or vertical tillage refers to a system where the arable land is prepared with equipment which does not invert the soil and which cause little compaction. For this reason, the surface normally remains with a good cover of residues on the surface.
- Ridge tillage is a system of ridges and furrows. The ridges may be narrow or wide and the furrows can be parallel to the contour lines or constructed with a slight slope, depending on whether the objective is to conserve moisture or to drain excess moisture. The ridges can be semi-permanent or be constructed each year which will govern the amount of residue material that remains on the surface.

Conventional tillage refers to the arable land treated by conventional tillage which involves inversion of the soil, normally with a mouldboard or a disc plough as the primary tillage operation, followed by secondary tillage with a disc harrow.

Zero tillage refers to the arable land on which no tillage is applied between harvest and sowing. Zero tillage is a minimum tillage practice in which the crop is sown directly into soil not tilled since the harvest of the previous crop. Weed control is achieved by the use of herbicides and/or appropriate mulching and stubble is retained for erosion control.

The **Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)** is the European Union agricultural policy, established under Article 33 of the Treaty establishing the European Community. The CAP is aimed at helping European farmers meet the need to feed more than 500 million Europeans. Its main objectives are to provide a stable, sustainably produced supply of safe food at affordable prices for consumers, while also ensuring a decent standard of living for 22 million farmers and agricultural workers. The CAP is one of the most important EU policies from a budget point of view: agricultural spending accounts for around 40% of the EU budget. The legal framework is adopted jointly by the Council and the European Parliament. The implementation of the CAP is the responsibility of the Member States. The CAP has changed a lot since it was established in 1962 and continues to change today. The CAP 2014-2020 focuses on three priorities: viable food production, sustainable management of natural resources, and balanced development of rural areas throughout the EU.

1 Introduction

The primary goal of Work Package 1 (WP 1) "Agrarian landscape characterization and cartography" is to deeply understand the evolving dynamics within the agricultural landscapes of Europe and Turkey. This work package explores the complex interaction between the agricultural environment and the implementation of soil-based agroecological measures, which is crucial to the broader scope of the Into-DIALOGUE project. The core value of Into-DIALOGUE is rooted in the collaborative efforts among farmers, scientists, policymakers, and other relevant stakeholders, aiming to create a conducive environment for sustainable agricultural practices.

This project emphasizes the importance of a solid understanding of land use distribution, soil attributes, and the recent amendments in the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) for the period 2023-2027. Careful consideration of these elements brings us closer to the primary objective of Into-DIALOGUE: aligning agricultural methodologies with sustainable agroecological principles, thus enhancing the agricultural harmony with the ecological environment.

Within the diverse agricultural landscapes of Europe and Turkey, smallholdings emerge as a crucial component. Into-DIALOGUE adopts the methodology to explore the synergies among farm attributes, farmers' ecological identities, and policy frameworks. This analytical approach fosters a deep understanding of the interaction among these factors, and how they collectively impact the adoption of soil-based agroecological practices.

The purpose of this document is to describe the results obtained by the working team of Task 1.1 "To select indicators for the characterization of the attributes that can affect the application of soil-based agroecological measures". The study outlines the identification of indicators that emphasise the degree of soil-based agroecological techniques across Europe and Turkey. Thematic maps are employed to showcase these indicators, creating a holistic portrayal of farming system properties and the predominance of agroecological systems.

To provide a consolidated, comprehensive, and clear narrative, this document combines what was initially slated to be three distinct deliverables under WP 1. These are:

- D1.1: Maps with selected parameters characterizing EU and Turkish agrarian landscapes. This aims to depict the expanse of sustainable agricultural practices.
- D1.2: Presentation of the results of the farms characteristics. Explaining the results among soil-based attributes, practices, and agroecological measures.
- D1.3: Indicators for the characterization of the attributes that can affect the application of soil-based agroecological measures. Encompassing farm characteristics, associated indicators, and bundles among attributes.

By combining these three deliverables into a single document, we aim to create a smooth narrative transition, enhancing the coherence and the ease of reference for all readers and stakeholders, thereby significantly contributing to the collaborative nature of Into-DIALOGUE. This deliverable is structured as follows:

- Introduction (Chapter 1).
- Methodology (Chapter 2).
- Distribution of agricultural land in Europe and Turkey (Chapter 3).
- Agrarian landscape characterization maps (Chapter 4).

2 Methodology

This report aims to answer the two objectives of Task 1.1, as described in the Into-DIALOGUE proposal. First, “to identify indicators of the total areas under application of soil-based agroecological measures, to produce thematic maps”. Second, “to quantify the relation among the size of the farms, the number of farms, and the areas under CAP payments and Turkish measures”. To address these research objectives, a thorough process of data collection, analysis, and visualization was conducted.

The geographic focus of the study was deliberately concentrated on seven countries: Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, and Turkey. These are the nations participating in the Into-DIALOGUE project. The study area covers a very representative diagonal transect of the different agricultural realities of the EU: from the South of Europe to the Northeast, including various climatic regions. The participation of Turkey enriches the content of the study; the extension of the cultivation area in this country, as well as the high proportion of young farmers it contributes, allows us to assess whether the new generations are more favourable to adopting agroecological practices related to soil management.

The methodology used to examine the distribution of agricultural land in Europe and Turkey (Chapter 3) and the creation of the agrarian landscape characterization maps (Chapter 4) are explained. These two chapters constitute the outcome of our research.

The first part of the results was combined in Chapter 3. This chapter focuses on the distribution of agricultural land in Europe and Turkey, and is based on an initial question from the project’s proposal: what is the connection between the distribution of agricultural land, and the distribution of the number of farms in Europe and Turkey? This was the main research question that we answered in Chapter 3 and influenced (even dictated) large parts of the rest of this document. Another influence was the main parameter we used across the chapter to analyse agricultural land: Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA), which is defined in the Eurostat glossary as “the total area taken up by arable land, permanent grassland, permanent crops and kitchen gardens used by the holding, regardless of the type of tenure or of whether it is used as a part of common land” (with “holding” being equal to farm unit in this deliverable).

Eurostat’s database (2016, 2020) was the main source of information used in Chapter 3. It provided the necessary information to answer Chapter 3.1 (Hectares of land vs. number of farms), Chapter 3.2 (Agricultural area distribution of Eurostat crops in Europe and Turkey), Chapter 3.3 (Distribution of tillage practices of arable land in Europe and Turkey), Chapter 3.4 (Distribution of farmers’ sex in Europe and Turkey), and Chapter 3.5 (Distribution of farmers’ age in Europe and Turkey).

Chapters’ 3.1 and 3.2 data was extracted from the “Main farm land use by NUTS 2 regions” folder (Eurostat, 2020), Chapter’s 3.3 data was extracted from the “Agricultural practices” folder (Eurostat, 2016), and chapters’ 3.4 and 3.5 data was extracted from the “Farm indicators by age and sex of the manager, economic size of the farm, utilised agricultural area and NUTS2 region” folder (Eurostat, 2020). The datasets used for Turkey mainly came from the Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK, 2016, 2020, 2023), Dogan (2019), BUGEM (2020), and Anadolu Agency (2023).

Finally, Chapter’s 3.6 (Analysis of the CAP subsidies and budget for EU Into-DIALOGUE countries) data was drawn from two reports from the European Commission: the 15th Financial Report on the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (European Commission, 2022), and the 15th Financial Report on the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (European Commission, 2022).

We systematically conducted an analysis for each of the datasets, which was mostly similar among the Eurostat datasets, except for chapters 3.2 and 3.3. In these two chapters, the data did not need any special handling. For the rest (Chapters 3.1, 3.4, and 3.5), there was a constant analysis of the

results acquired from using either hectares of land or number of farms as a unit of measure. Most importantly, the comparison between the results from each of these choices was thoroughly studied, becoming a central point of this deliverable. Regarding Chapter 3.6, the data from the reports (European Commission, 2022) was simply extracted and presented in percentages to facilitate its understanding.

The analysis from Chapter 3.1 required some additional modifications of the data. The farm sizes were adapted to be able to include the data from Turkey (TÜİK, 2016) with the European countries (Eurostat, 2016). Furthermore, the bracket of farms smaller than zero hectares was removed. This was done for two reasons: we did not consider that a farms smaller than zero hectares should be considered an “agricultural practice” since it would hardly provide economic sustainability (1), and it disrupted the rest of the analysis (figures and percentages) due to the sheer number of farms in this bracket. To complement the analysis of this chapter, the Gini Index was calculated and the Lorenz Curve created (Figure 3.5).

One of the key objectives of T1.1 is to assess the level of heterogeneity in the distribution of the land among farmers. Here, the need to find an index capable of measuring the dichotomy in the distribution of the agricultural land between small and large farms in the countries involved in the task. For this purpose, we decided to use an adapted version of the Gini index, commonly used in economics to measure the statistical dispersion of income, wealth, consumption within a nation or a social group to measures their degree of inequality.

In light of that, to measure the heterogeneity in the distribution of the land among farmers we calculated the frequency distribution of the agricultural land by the official Eurostat land classes and frequency distribution of the number of farmers by the same classes for the different countries involved in the project.

As a first step we created a land distribution curve, coined the Lorenz Curve, with the x-axis representing the cumulative frequency distribution of the land and the y-axis the cumulative frequency distribution of the number of farms (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1. Lorenz curve and Gini Index methodology representation. Graphical representation of the method adopted to calculate the heterogeneity in the distribution of the land among farmers.

Figure 2.1 depicts two lines: 1) the 45-degree line is the ideal identity function (the agricultural land is distributed homogeneously among farms); 2) the curved line is the actual distribution of the land among farms. The region of the plane between these two curves is labelled by Γ , and it provides a measure of the heterogeneity in the distribution of the land among farmers. As a complement, the region of the plane between the curved line and the x axis is labelled by Λ . By construction the area below the 45-degree line equals $\frac{1}{2}$, as a consequence:

$$\Gamma = 1/2 - \Lambda \quad (1)$$

To let this index 0-1 ranging we must multiply it by 2, obtaining the Gini index, G, as follows:

$$G = 1 - 2\Lambda \quad (2)$$

Thus, to derive G we need to calculate the area. As for example, by breaking the area in Figure 2.1 into three triangles and two rectangles we find this area to be as follows:

$$\Lambda = 1/2 ab + (c-a)b + 1/2 (c-a)(d-b) + (1-c)d + 1/2 (1-c)(1-d) \quad (3)$$

Simplifying, we get:

$$\Lambda = 1/2 [cb - ad + d + 1 - c] \quad (4)$$

By substituting it into eq. 2 we finally obtain the desired index:

$$G = c - d + ad - bc \quad (5)$$

The above procedure was followed to calculate the G indexes on the 7 modified Eurostat classes of agricultural land for the Countries represented in Into-DIALOGUE. There are some limits in interpreting a Gini coefficient, as the same value may result from many different distribution curves. To mitigate this, the demographic structure of the farms can be considered, as it is done in chapter 3.4 and 3.5.

For Chapter 4, a comprehensive agrarian landscape characterization was undertaken. The analysis focused on several key factors, including soil types (Chapter 4.1), texture (Chapter 4.2), organic carbon content (Chapter 4.3), as well as land use/cover across selected European countries and Turkey (Chapter 4.4), crop selection (Chapter 4.5), and soil health impacts (Chapter 4.1). Advanced geospatial tools, such as ArcGIS Pro, were instrumental in mapping and modifying these landscape characteristics to fit the needs of the project.

To delineate the distribution of soil types, two distinct maps were employed. The first was adapted, based on the information provided by the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC; Panagos, 2016). The second was directly extracted from the Soil Atlas of Europe (European Commission, 2005). Notably, only the latter incorporated data for Turkey. Both maps abide by the first level soil classification as defined by the World Reference Base for Soil Resources (WRB). To understand the differences between maps, we contacted ESDAC via email. Regarding the non-inclusion of Turkey in the downloadable dataset in comparison to the Atlas, we were informed that "The soil map in the Atlas added Turkey data that were never 'officially' integrated in the ESDB" (M. van Liedekerke, personal communication, 11th September, 2023). Regarding the differences between the data and the Soil Atlas of Europe, the response from ESDAC (J. Arwyn, personal communication, 13th September,

2023) was:

“The difference between your map and the one in the atlas reflects two issues:

- how the dominant STU is assigned.
- discussions on the correctness of translation of the codes from the FAO legend to the version of WRB that existed at the time.

In the former, it is possible that in cases where two STUs a dominant in a polygon, some expert judgment was applied.

For the second point, the easiest solution is to look at the legend of the atlas on pages 40-41 to see how the updated translation was applied.

For example, the FAO code Bk (Calcic Cambisol) was interpreted as a Haplic Calcisol, as the calcic properties were deemed to overrule the cambic ones, thus making it a Calcisol. In a similar manner, the Bh polygons of northwestern Spain were regarded as a Haplic Umbrisol rather than an Umbric Cambisol.”

An in-depth commentary accompanies these maps, analysing the visualized patterns and their implications for the regions.

Soil texture plays a crucial role in soil behaviour and its interaction with water and crops. Two soil texture maps were reviewed for this purpose. The first was sourced from ESDAC (Ballabio et al., 2016), excluding Turkey. Meanwhile, the second map was adopted from Poggio et al. (2021), which offers a derived layer illustrating the predominant soil texture up to a depth of 1 meter, with texture class definitions attributed to the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA). This map presents a resolution of 250m and includes Turkey. Chapter 4.2 also includes some comments to aid in interpreting the displayed texture variations.

Chapter 4.3 showcases topsoil organic carbon content in the soil, which has been linked with soil health and fertility. Drawing on the work of Poggio et al. (2021), a derived layer estimating the carbon content of soils up to a depth of 30 centimetres was used to show the properties of Into-DIALOGUE countries soils. The carbon content is quantified as grams of carbon per kilogram of soil (g C kg⁻¹) and is visualized at a resolution of 250m. The nuances of the map are briefly discussed, highlighting areas with notable carbon densities.

Chapter 4.4 focuses on land use/cover, which is key for understanding Europe and Turkey’s agrarian landscape, for agricultural planning and decision-making. For this section, a specialized map was constructed generated using European Union's Copernicus Land Monitoring Service information (2020). The map shows the land use/cover across Into-DIALOGUE countries including Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, and Turkey. The original CORINE (Coordination of information on the Environment) dataset, consisting of 44 classes, was reclassified into 9 simplified classes for the year 2018. In this dataset, satellite data from Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 were used for gap filling. The reclassification, based on the combination of using the “Updated CLC illustrated nomenclature guidelines” (European Union's Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2020), satellite image comparison of multiple sites, and expert knowledge, was done as follows:

- Settlements. Includes: “Continuous urban fabric”, “Discontinuous urban fabric”, “Industrial or commercial units”, “Road and rail networks and associated land”, “Port areas”, “Airports”, “Mineral extraction sites”, “Dump sites”, “Construction sites”, “Green urban areas”, and “Sport and leisure facilities”.
- Forests and shrubs. Includes: “Broad-leaved forest”, “Coniferous forest”, “Mixed forest”, “Sclerophyllous vegetation”, “Transitional woodland-shrub”, and “Sparsely vegetated area”.

- Grasslands. Includes: “Pastures”, “Natural grasslands”, and “Moors and heathland”.
- Wetlands. Includes: “Inland marshes”, “Peat bogs”, “Salt marshes”, and “Salines”.
- Water bodies. Includes: “Water courses”, “Water bodies”, “Coastal lagoons”, “Estuaries”, “Sea and ocean”.
- Permanent tree crops. Includes: “Vineyards”, “Fruit trees and berry plantations”, “Olive groves”, and “Annual crops associated with permanent crops”.
- Agricultural land (crop unspecified). Includes: “Non-irrigated arable land”, “Permanently irrigated land”, “Complex cultivation patterns”, and “Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation”.
- Rice. Only “Rice fields” included.
- Others. Includes: “Beaches, dunes, sands”, “Bare rocks”, “Glaciers and perpetual snow”, and “Intertidal flats”.

Expanding upon the previous map, Chapter 4.5 combines the “Land use/cover map” from Chapter 4.4 (Figure 4.4) with a crop selection layer based on in-situ data from Eurostat LUCAS (Land Use/Cover Area frame Survey) and observations from Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR). This layer from d’Andrimont et al. (2021) has a resolution of 10 meters (which is exceptionally precise) and 80.3% accuracy overall. Despite this, Turkey was not available as part of this dataset. The detailed 23 classes originally present were reclassified into 8 simplified classes. This helped improve accuracy by comparing with satellite images and selecting the most appropriate class from either CORINE or SAR-LUCAS. The reclassification was the following:

- Wheat. Includes: “Common wheat” and “durum wheat”.
- Other cereals. Includes: “Oats”, “barley”, “triticale”, “rye”, and “other cereals”.
- Maize. Remains untouched.
- Root crops. Includes: “Potatoes”, “sugar beets”, and “other root crops”.
- Sunflower. Remains untouched.
- Turnip rape and rapeseed. Remains untouched.
- Protein crops. Includes: “Soya”, and “dry pulses”.
- Fodder crops. Remains untouched.
- All other items from the original layer were considered as NODATA. This includes: “Artificial”, “rice”, “other non-permanent industrial crops”, “bare arable land”, “woodland and shrubland”, “grass land”, and “bare land”.

Most of the land use/cover classes from CORINE were considered more accurate after comparing with satellite images. This includes “Forests and shrubs”, “Grassland”, “Settlements” or “Artificial”, “Bare land”, “Rice”, “Permanent crop trees”, and “Others”. Hence, the addition from d’Andrimont et al. (2021) provided with a detailed crop selection, while the unknown agricultural land (usually due to no data from SAR-LUCAS) remained as “Agricultural land (crop unspecified)” from CORINE. After multiple comparisons with satellite images, the “Rice” and “Permanent tree crops” from CORINE were decided to overrule the classification from SAR-LUCAS, since those were considered to represent the European landscape much more accurately.

Adding another dimension to the analysis, the impact of land use and crop selection on soil health was mapped. The data layers were the same as Chapter 4.5, stemming from CORINE and SAR/LUCAS datasets. However, an essential distinction was the reclassification of the original 23 classes into 4

classes based on literature and expert insights. The map is complemented by an explanation of the reclassification, which while subjective, is still based on a body of literature. The reclassification was the following:

- Mild impact crops. Includes “Common wheat”, “durum wheat”, “oats”, “barley”, “triticale”, “rye”, and “other cereals”.
- Risky crops. Includes: “Maize”, “sunflower”, “turnip rape and rapeseed”, “potatoes”, and “sugar beets”.
- Beneficial impact crops. Includes: “Soya” and “dry pulses”.
- Variable impact crops. Includes “Other root crops” and “fodder crops”.
- All other items from the original layer were considered as NODATA, like in the previous classification from Chapter 4.5.

3 Distribution of Agricultural Land in Europe and Turkey

This chapter focuses on describing the distribution of agricultural land in Europe and Turkey. To achieve this, several key elements have been analysed, which are divided into six sub-chapters. The chapter is divided as follows. Chapter 3.1 focuses on the relation between number of farms and hectares of land across Into-DIALOGUE countries. Chapter 3.2 analyses the crop type distribution in the countries involved. Chapter 3.3 informs about the distribution of tillage practices across Europe. Chapter 3.4 focuses on analysing the gender distribution of farm managers, while Chapter 3.5 focuses on their age. Finally, Chapter 3.6 expands on the economical perspective through an analysis of the CAP (Common Agricultural Policy) subsidies and budget for Into-DIALOGUE countries.

Most of the data used in this chapter comes from the Eurostat database website. Turkey's data is not included in Eurostat, so it has been added, when possible, with collaboration from our Turkey's partner (TAGEM).

3.1 Hectares of land vs. number of farms

The results from this part of the chapter are mainly summarized in Figure 3.1. Italy, Poland and Turkey have the highest number of farms, followed by Spain, Lithuania and Latvia, and Czech Republic. These are absolute values however, not accounting for the total area of the country. Figures 3.2 and 3.3 show the results for all countries next to each other, relative to their total number of farms and hectares of land respectively, making the contrast between landowners more noticeable.

Figure 3.2 shows that the concentration of small farms (those less than 10 ha in size) is evident across Into-DIALOGUE countries. With 68% of farms fitting this category, Italy, Turkey, and Poland demonstrate the highest prevalence, highlighting the role of smallholdings in these countries. This contrasts sharply with Czechia, where smaller farms make up a much lower percentage of the total. In Czechia, the farms than 100 ha, encompass a staggering 86,5% of the agricultural land. Spain, Latvia, and Lithuania also display pronounced land concentration in farms larger than 100 ha, owning 57,8%, 63,8%, and 54,9% of the land, respectively. However, Poland and Turkey deviate from this trend, showing a more equitable distribution of land across various farm sizes.

Figure 3.3 accentuates the uneven ownership distribution of agricultural land in Into-DIALOGUE countries. In particular, farms larger than 50 ha, which constitute less than 10% of the total farm ownership, possess 60% of the land. This disparity becomes even more pronounced for farms larger than 100 ha. Here, 5% of owners have 47% of the land. Czechia exhibits the most pronounced disparity. Although farms larger than 100 ha constitute only 17,3% of the total farms, they hold 86,5% of the land. Meanwhile, countries like Italy and Turkey present an opposing scenario. In Italy, for instance, while 39,8% of the farms are smaller than 2 ha, they collectively occupy just 3,4% of the agricultural land. This indicates a prevalence of small farm structures in Italy but with limited agricultural land under this group.

There's a visible disconnect between farm size and land ownership. In countries like Czechia, a smaller number of larger farms predominate. Conversely, in countries such as Italy, Turkey, and Poland, while small farms are numerically predominant, their collective landholding remains minimal. This discrepancy between farm numbers and land area highlights the challenges faced by smallholder farmers in accessing land resources and might reflect historical, social, economic, and policy-driven factors. This is addressed in Chapter 3.6, where the influence of European subsidies for agriculture is analysed.

Figure 3.1. Distribution of farms in Into-DIALOGUE countries. For each country there is an associated graph that indicates: number of farms (brown bars) and farm size in hectares (bar colour varies per country). Source: Eurostat (2020) and TÜİK (2016); links: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_LUS_MAIN/default/table?lang=en & <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Tarimsal--Isletme-Yapi-Arastirmasi-2016-24869>

Figure 3.2. Distribution of farms (of Utilised Agricultural Area) in Into-DIALOGUE countries (Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, and Turkey). Farm sizes in hectares are divided into seven brackets, from smaller (left) to bigger (right). The red square indicates the brackets where most of the farms are contained. Source: Eurostat (2020); link:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_LUS_MAIN/default/table?lang=en

Figure 3.3. Distribution of hectares (of Utilised Agricultural Area) in Into-DIALOGUE countries (Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, and Turkey). Farm sizes in hectares are divided into seven brackets, from smaller (left) to bigger (right). The red square indicates the brackets where most of the land is contained. Source: Eurostat (2020) and TÜİK (2016); links:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_LUS_MAIN/default/table?lang=en
 & <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Tarimsal--Isletme-Yapi-Arastirmasi-2016-24869>

The Into-DIALOGUE project is focused on Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, and Turkey. Regardless, we considered important to understand the distribution of land and farms across all Europe, to provide an overall picture of the continent. Figure 3.4 shows that in the rest of the EU countries, there is a similar trend: 8% of owners possess 74% of land, in farms bigger than 50 ha. This has an influence in CAP subsidies.

Percentage of farms and ha (%) related to farm size (ha) Countries of the EU (without Into-Dialogue countries)

Figure 3.4. Distribution of hectares of land and number of farms (of Utilised Agricultural Area) in Europe, excluding Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, and Latvia. Farm sizes in hectares are divided into seven brackets, from smaller (left) to bigger (right). The red square indicates the brackets where most of the land is contained. Source: Eurostat (2020); link: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_LUS_MAIN/default/table?lang=en

The Gini Index and Lorenz curve are statistical measures to gauge inequality. Higher values (lines farther from the center of the graph) indicate a higher degree of inequality. In Figure 3.5, the distribution of land in hectares, and the distribution of the number of farms, are thus combined as explained in the methodology (Chapter 2). By looking at both the Gini Index (table) and the graph’s lines for each country, it can be depicted that Latvia and Spain are the most unequal, since their GIs are the highest and their lines are the farthest away from the line of perfect equality (not in a single point of the graph, like the Czech Republic, but on average throughout the whole graph). On the other hand, Poland and Turkey are the most equal for the opposite reasons. This provides a new insight, showcasing that in some areas there is more equality between landowners than initially thought. This is the case of the Czech Republic with a GI of 0,25. Here, despite having 86,5% of the land in farms larger than 100 ha, they are owned by 17,3% of farmers. This is a remarkably high number of big landowners compared to the rest of the countries.

Figure 3.5. Lorenz curve (figure on the left) and Gini Index (table on the right). There is a Lorenz curve for each country (the colour of the line is assigned next to the country's name), depicting the value from the GI (Gini Index) table next to it. The straight black diagonal line in the middle of the figure indicates perfect equality. Source: Eurostat (2020) and TÜİK (2016); links:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_LUS_MAIN/default/table?lang=en

& <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Tarimsal-Isletme-Yapi-Arastirmasi-2016-24869>

3.2 Agricultural area distribution of Eurostat crops in Europe and Turkey

Italy (1.936.500 hectares) and Spain (1.871.600 hectares) lead in absolute terms of land either fully converted or under conversion to organic farming. This changes when looking at the relative values compared to the UAA: Italy has the highest proportion of its UAA dedicated to organic farming at 15.5%, Czechia closely follows Italy with 15.1%, Latvia also has a significant 14.5%, Spain and Lithuania have less than 8% of their UAA dedicated to organic farming, and Poland has the smallest proportion with only 3.4% (Table 3.1).

Poland and Spain have the highest arable land, indicating significant crop-based farming. This trend is even stronger when considering arable land relative to UAA, showing that Poland uses 75.4% of its UAA for arable land. Spain and Italy possess extensive permanent grassland (7.533.350 and 3.133.800 respectively), often associated with livestock grazing. Spain still maintains a higher relative use of its UAA for permanent grassland (31.5%) compared to Italy (25%), but the difference is less pronounced in relative terms (Table 3.1). While Turkey is the biggest country of the project, the different data source makes the comparison with other countries difficult, since the methodology used to determine these numbers was different. However, it is clear that arable land (19.586.000 ha) is highly dominant.

Spain and Italy also show dominant permanent crops, which likely reflects their Mediterranean climate, suitable for crops like olives, grapes, and citrus fruits. Regarding unutilised agricultural area, the numbers for Italy and Latvia are quite high, but that be due to fallow lands or those awaiting agricultural development (Table 3.1).

In summary, Table 3.1 underscores the diverse agricultural landscapes and priorities across these

European countries, reflecting their unique environmental conditions and agricultural strategies.

Table 3.1. Distribution of crops across European agricultural area in hectares for Into-DIALOGUE countries. Source: BUGEM (2020), Eurostat (2020), and TÜİK (2023), links:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_LUS_MAIN/default/table?lang=en

[https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Kategori/GetKategori?p=Tarim-111\(2020\)](https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Kategori/GetKategori?p=Tarim-111(2020))

<https://www.tarimorman.gov.tr/sgb/Belgeler/SagMenuVeriler/BUGEM.pdf>

CROPS	Czechia	Italy	Latvia	Lithuania	Poland	Spain	Turkey
Total farm area	4.923.130	16.462.350	2.830.130	3.085.880	16.662.370	28.929.890	37.762.000
Utilised agricultural area (UAA)	3.492.570	12.523.540	1.968.960	2.914.550	14.784.120	23.913.680	23.145.000
Fully converted and under conversion to organic farming utilised agricultural area (excluding kitchen gardens)	528.310	1.936.500	285.500	233.590	501.160	1.871.600	381.277
Arable land	2.476.710	7.197.650	1.333.290	2.237.320	11.147.160	11.714.690	19.586.000
Permanent grassland - outdoor	978.090	3.133.800	626.140	650.320	3.235.050	7.533.350	2.138.413
Permanent crops	36.140	2.176.660	7.580	26.900	378.760	4.657.180	3.559.000
Kitchen gardens - outdoor	140	13.960	1.950	0	21.930	2.740	779.000
Cultivated mushrooms	0	200	No data	10	250	310	76
Unutilised agricultural area	6.560	317.990	72.860	16.520	174.820	53.380	3.173.000
Wooded areas	1.308.590	2.950.600	626.200	110.890	956.830	2.140.570	23.110.000
Other areas on the farms	115.410	670.010	162.100	43.910	746.360	2.821.950	5.000

3.3 Distribution of tillage practices of arable land in Europe

Table 3.2 shows that Italy and Latvia have significant portions of their arable land not under any form of tillage. The reasons might range from fallow lands, land awaiting different agricultural operations, or non-tillable lands due to specific constraints, e.g. relatively low soil fertility, location or distribution in marginal areas, emptying of rural areas, etc. On the other hand, conventional tillage is dominant in all countries, with Poland and Spain leading in absolute numbers. This reflects the longstanding and widespread use of this traditional land preparation method in Europe. Regarding conservational tillage, Spain stands out with a significant portion of its land (2.020.150 hectares) under conservational tillage, emphasizing a shift towards sustainable and soil-conserving farming practices. Spain also leads in zero tillage practices, with 739.130 hectares, highlighting a progressive approach to land management that reduces soil disturbance. Poland and Italy follow, but with considerably less land under this method (Table 3.2).

When analysing the data relative to the total arable land of each country, Czechia has the highest proportion of its arable land under conservational tillage (31,3%), followed by Spain (17,6%). Poland and Italy have the lowest percentages, indicating a preference for other tillage practices. For zero tillage practices relative to total arable land, Spain still leads in the adoption of such measures (6,4%), followed by Italy (3,2%).

In summary, while conventional tillage remains prevalent in these European countries, there's a noticeable move towards more sustainable tillage practices, especially evident in Spain. The variation across countries suggests different agricultural strategies and priorities influenced by factors like soil types, climate, and socio-economic considerations.

Table 3.2. Distribution of tillage practices in Europe's arable land in hectares, for Into-DIALOGUE countries, excluding Turkey. Source: Eurostat (2016), link:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_MP_PRAC/default/table?lang=en

TILLAGE	Total arable land	Arable land excluding tillage	Conventional tillage	Conservational tillage	Zero tillage
Czechia	2.473.220	63.710	1.603.520	772.550	33.440
Italy	7.145.040	907.470	5.742.750	263.410	231.420
Latvia	1.284.650	358.670	844.770	68.390	12.820
Lithuania	2.130.250	157.380	1.745.680	201.420	25.760
Poland	10.805.610	160.640	10.121.640	296.630	226.700
Spain	11.462.910	304.160	8.399.480	2.020.150	739.130

3.4 Distribution of farmers' gender in Europe and Turkey

Figures 3.6 and 3.7, and Tables 3.3 and 3.4, show that agriculture in countries participating in the Into-DIALOGUE project is mainly dominated by men. Although the general trend in Europe over the last decades points to an increase in females in the agricultural sector (Eurostat, 2016), this is still the case. The comparison between the land (hectares) and number of farms held by each gender is especially interesting, with results indicating that the average size farm is 37 hectares for males and 22 hectares for females. This means that on average, farms managed by men are about 60% bigger than those managed by women .

There is, however, variability in these distributions between countries. The discrepancy between the number of farms and the total hectares of farmland in Latvia and Lithuania is particularly noteworthy. In both countries, women appear to be prominently involved in the agricultural sector, owning 45% of farms. However, these farms account for only 25% and 24% of the total agricultural land (measured in hectares) in Latvia and Lithuania, respectively (Figures 3.6 and 3.7, Tables 3.3 and 3.4). While in Turkey the number of female managers is very low (13%), they still account for 10% of the land.

Figure 3.6. Distribution of hectares of Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) by gender of the manager, represented in percentages for Into-DIALOGUE countries. Source: Anadolu Agency (2023), Dogan (2019), Eurostat (2020), and TÜİK (2020), links:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_M_FARMANG/default/table?lang=en
<https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Isgucu-Istatistikleri-2022-49390>

UAA (Utilized Agricultural Area) distribution by gender (%) - Number of farms

Figure 3.7. Distribution of number of farms of Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) by gender of the manager, represented in percentages for Into-DIALOGUE countries. Source: Eurostat (2020) and TÜİK (2020), link:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_M_FARMANG/default/table?lang=en
<https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Isgucu-Istatistikleri-2022-49390>

Table 3.3. Distribution of hectares of Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) by gender of the manager, represented in percentages for Into-DIALOGUE countries. Source: Anadolu Agency (2023), Dogan (2019), Eurostat (2020), and TÜİK (2020), links:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_M_FARMANG/default/table?lang=en
<https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Isgucu-Istatistikleri-2022-49390>

SEX	Total	Males	Females	% Males	% Females
Czechia	3.492.570	3.029.120	463.450	87%	13%
Italy	12.041.230	9.301.160	2.740.070	77%	23%
Latvia	1.968.960	1.471.760	497.200	75%	25%
Lithuania	2.914.550	2.212.380	702.170	76%	24%
Poland	14.749.240	10.693.660	4.055.580	73%	27%
Spain	23.913.680	19.238.810	4.674.870	80%	20%
Turkey	23.145.000	20.888.363	2.256.637	90%	10%

Table 3.4. Distribution of number of farms of Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) by gender of the manager, represented in percentages for Into-DIALOGUE countries. Source: Eurostat (2020) and TÜİK (2020), link:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_M_FARMANG/default/table?lang=en
<https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Isgucu-Istatistikleri-2022-49390>

SEX	Total	Males	Females	% Males	% Females
Czechia	28.910	23.670	5.240	82%	18%
Italy	1.130.530	774.760	355.770	69%	31%
Latvia	68.980	38.100	30.890	55%	45%
Lithuania	132.080	72.740	59.340	55%	45%
Poland	1.301.490	853.370	448.120	66%	34%
Spain	914.870	653.300	261.570	71%	29%
Turkey	3.022.130	2.617.163	404.968	87%	13%

3.5 Distribution of farmers' age in Europe and Turkey

The brackets for the age distribution used in this chapter are based on the simplification of the main societal life phases into four categories. This approach considers significant milestones and general life patterns in society.

- Young Adults: Less than 25 years (early education and early career years).
- Early Career: From 25 to 44 years (typically when individuals establish their careers).
- Mid-Career: From 45 to 64 years (peak earning years and preparation for retirement).
- Seniors: 65 years or over (retirement phase).

In Figure 3.8 and Table 3.5, Lithuania and Poland have the highest percentage of land managed by the youngest age group, at 13%. Spain, in contrast, has the lowest at 5%. Regarding mid-age farmers, Poland leads with 39% of its agricultural land managed by this age group, while Spain lags at only 20%. The farmers included in the 45 to 64 years bracket, manage the majority of agricultural land across all countries, with Turkey having the highest percentage at 76%, and Czechia following with 59%. Finally, Italy and Spain have the highest percentage of land managed by the oldest age group at 27%, while Poland has the lowest at 10%.

Farm indicator by the age of the manager and hectares of land in the country

Figure 3.8. Distribution of hectares of Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) by age, divided in four age brackets (young adults, less than 25 years; early career, from 25 to 44 years; mid-career, from 45 to 64 years; and seniors, 65 years or over) and represented in percentages for Into-DIALOGUE countries. Source: Eurostat (2020) and TÜİK (2020), link:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_M_FARMANG/default/table?lang=en
<https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Isgucu-Istatistikleri-2022-49390>

Table 3.5. Distribution of hectares of Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) by age, divided in four age brackets (young adults, less than 25 years; early career, from 25 to 44 years; mid-career, from 45 to 64 years; and seniors, 65 years or over) and represented in percentages for Into-DIALOGUE countries. Source: Eurostat (2020) and TÜİK (2020), link:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_M_FARMANG/default/table?lang=en
<https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Isgucu-Istatistikleri-2022-49390>

AGE	< 25	25 to 44	45 to 64	> 65
Czechia	6%	24%	59%	16%
Italy	8%	22%	49%	27%
Latvia	10%	26%	58%	16%
Lithuania	13%	32%	52%	15%
Poland	13%	39%	50%	10%
Spain	5%	20%	53%	27%
Turkey	1%	28%	76%	8%

Figure 3.9 and Table 3.6 show that most countries have a very low percentage of farms managed by the youngest age group, generally around 1%, with Latvia and Spain at 0,5%. For early career farmers (25 to 44 years), Turkey has the highest percentage at 42%, while Czechia and Poland hold the second and third position at 29% and 32% respectively. Italy and Spain have the lowest, with only 14% and 13% respectively. The older mid-career farmers manage the majority of the farms in every country. Latvia and Poland have the highest percentages at 54% and 53%, respectively. Finally, Italy and Lithuania show a significant number of farms managed by the oldest age group at 43% and 32% respectively. Poland has the lowest at 14%.

Figure 3.9. Distribution of number of farms of Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) by age, divided in four age brackets (young adults, less than 25 years; early career, from 25 to 44 years; mid-career, from 45 to 64 years; and seniors, 65 years or over) and represented in percentages for Into-DIALOGUE countries. Source: Eurostat (2020) and TÜİK (2020), link:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_M_FARMANG/default/table?lang=en
<https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Isgucu-Istatistikleri-2022-49390>

Table 3.6. Distribution of number of farms of Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) by age, divided in four age brackets (young adults, less than 25 years; early career, from 25 to 44 years; mid-career, from 45 to 64 years; and seniors, 65 years or over) and represented in percentages for Into-DIALOGUE countries. Source: Eurostat (2020) and TÜİK (2020), link:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_M_FARMANG/default/table?lang=en
<https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Isgucu-Istatistikleri-2022-49390>

AGE	< 25	25 to 44	45 to 64	> 65
Czechia	1,2%	29%	49%	21%
Italy	0,9%	14%	43%	43%
Latvia	0,5%	16%	54%	30%
Lithuania	0,6%	17%	50%	32%
Poland	1,2%	32%	53%	14%
Spain	0,5%	13%	45%	41%
Turkey	1,3%	42%	49%	8%

The comparative analysis of all figures and tables of Chapter 3.5, reveals the increasing importance of young farmers. In Czechia, young farmers manage 1.2% of farms, yet oversee 6% of the land. Poland displays a similar pattern, where young farmers handle 1.2% of farms but command 13% of the land. Lithuania's young farmers, although managing only 0.6% of the farms, oversee 13% of the land. In Spain, even though young farmers represent a mere 0.5% of farm managers, they account for 5% of the total farmland. Similarly, Italy's young farmers handle 0.9% of the farms but have control over 8% of the farmland. These patterns indicate that in countries like Poland, Lithuania, Spain, and even Italy, young farmers, despite being fewer in number, often run larger farms. This could be due to inheritances, new investments in farming, new generations studying specialized

agricultural degrees, or various agrarian policies that favour the consolidation of land under younger farmers. For early-career farmers, in countries like Poland, this age group manages a large percentage of both the land and the number of farms, suggesting they are central to the agricultural sector. The next farmers bracket (45 to 64 years) dominates consistently across Tables 3.5 and 3.6, indicating their continued prominence in the agricultural sector. Finally, when comparing the two tables, it's evident that while the oldest age group manages a higher percentage of farms, they oversee a relatively smaller proportion of total agricultural land.

The data suggests a changing dynamic in European agriculture, with the exception of Turkey. While the older generation continues to manage a significant number of farms, these tend to be smaller in size. In contrast, younger farmers, although fewer in number, manage a larger proportion of the agricultural land, indicating a shift towards larger, possibly more commercially oriented farming operations among the younger generation. The predominant role of the 45 to 64 age group in both tables underscores their critical importance in the present-day agricultural landscape of these countries (Figures 3.8 and 3.9, Tables 3.5 and 3.6).

3.6 Analysis of the CAP subsidies and budget for EU Into-DIALOGUE countries

The allocation of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) budget for 2021 to the European nations that are part of Into-DIALOGUE (which only excludes Turkey) provides critical insights into the agricultural focus and priorities of the European Union. In 2021, the CAP budget amounted to a substantial € 58.100,7 million, of which a significant fraction was divided amongst the Into-DIALOGUE nations (Table 3.7).

Spain stands out with the highest allocation at 11,73% or € 6.816,1 million, reflecting its prominence in the European agricultural landscape. Although it is not part of the project nor the analysis, France is the only country receiving more CAP subsidies than Spain. Italy follows closely with 9,83% or € 5.712,3 million, and Poland with an 8,21% or € 4.770,3 million further underscores their significant roles. Conversely, Latvia receives a minimal allocation of just 0,72% or € 421,2 million, indicating its smaller scale within the European agricultural context, also influenced by the country's smaller size.

It's noteworthy that in 2021, a majority of the CAP budget was directed towards direct payments and market measures, accounting for 76,8% under the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF). In contrast, rural development measures made up 23,2% under the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD).

Delving deeper into budget appropriations that focus on agroecological practices, significant emphasis was given to the "Payment for agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the environment," which received € 10.778,0 million from the EAGF. This indicates the EU's proactive approach to integrating sustainable farming practices. Other relevant allocations include the "Agri-environment-climate measures" and "Organic farming measures," which received € 2.352,7 million and € 1.177,7 million, respectively, from the EAFRD. These appropriations reflect the European Union's commitment to promoting environmentally friendly agricultural practices that cater to the dual goals of productivity and sustainability. The Into-DIALOGUE Deliverable 4.1 provides an in-depth analysis of CAP measures in these countries.

Table 3.7. Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) budget allocation for Into-DIALOGUE countries belonging to the EU (Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, and Latvia) in 2021. Source: European Commission, 15th Financial Reports on the EAGF (2022) and EAFRD (2022).

CAP budget in 2021			
Country	% of total EU	Millions of EUR	EUR per hectare
Czechia	2,11%	€ 1.226,5	€ 351
Italy	9,83%	€ 5.712,3	€ 474
Latvia	0,72%	€ 421,2	€ 214
Lithuania	1,21%	€ 703,7	€ 241
Poland	8,21%	€ 4.770,3	€ 323
Spain	11,73%	€ 6.816,1	€ 285
Not part of Into-DIALOGUE	66,18%	€ 38.450,6	€ 393
Total EU € 58.100,7			

4 Agrarian Landscape Characterization Maps

This chapter aims to inform about the characteristics of the European landscape in relation to soil health and agroecological measures. To achieve this, several maps and pictures have been created, which are divided into five sub-chapters. The chapter is divided as follows. Chapter 4.1 focuses on soil types across Into-DIALOGUE countries. Chapter 4.2 shows the soil textures present in Europe. Chapter 4.3 describes the soil organic carbon of the project's area. Chapter 4.4 presents the land use/cover of Into-DIALOGUE countries. Chapter 4.5 combines the land use/cover data with the crop selection present in Europe. Finally, Chapter 4.6 focuses on the crop's impact on soil health.

The data availability in this chapter highly varies between maps. In general, it is a combination of satellite data and *in-situ* observations. Turkey is sometimes not included (or officially included) in the same data files as the rest of Europe, for this reason its presence in the maps fluctuates.

4.1 Soil types

Figure 4.1 shows the result of the soil type map at the first classification level (group level) produced from the ESDAC data. In Latvia, predominant soil formation processes are podzolization, lessivage, leaching in soil evolution due to the climate conditions, where amount of precipitation exceeds evaporation. Luvisols and Phaeozems dominate in the lands used for agriculture, while Arenosols, Podzols and Albeluvisols or Retisols prevail in forest lands. Even though most of the agricultural lands are drained due to the dominance of precipitation over evaporation, in soils with a heavier granulometric composition, the soil cover is formed by Stagnosols. In flat topography regions with disturbed natural drainage and relatively high ground water table in uplands and depression valleys is important precondition for the development of gleyization process. In such conditions Gleysols are predominant soils, as well as Phaeozems and Histosols are formed due to accumulation of organic matter. As a result of the podzolization process, most of the soil is characterized by relatively low pH value, as a result of which large areas need to be limed.

Albeluvisols, Cambisols, and Phaeozems are represented in Lithuania. Podzols, Luvisols and Phaeozems are representative in Poland. Albeluvisols and Acrisols are extremely acidic soils with a low base saturation (<35 %) and a high concentration of exchangeable aluminium, with clay accumulation in the subsurface horizons composed of kaolinitic clay mineralogy (low cation exchange capacity and pH-dependent charge), and with a high Fe and Al oxide and oxyhydroxide content. If taken together all these properties, these soils are generally considered as soils with very low capacity for agricultural use. Agricultural use requires organic amendments and lime treatment to increase the pH, which enables controlling the Al³⁺ toxicity (generally saturated above the 60 % capacity value for sensitive crops), and the availability of P (adsorption is related to Fe oxides, Al, Mn, and amorphous or weakly crystalline aluminosilicate). Podzols are highly acidic, display low fertility, contain excessive permeability of the eluvial (leaching process) horizon, and sometimes characterized by a cementation of the subsurface cambic horizon. Taking all these properties into consideration, these soils are most frequently used for forestry.

Czech Republic, Italy and Spain have in common most of their territory covered by Cambisols (Figure 4.1). When added to Calcisols and Leptosols, these are also the most abundant soils in Turkey (Figure 4.2). Nevertheless, in Spain, according to Figure 4.1. Calcisols seem not be represented. When observed figures 4.3a and 4.3b, more than half of the territory in Spain, dominated by lime and calcaric rocks including clays and sediments, characterize by calcaric Cambisol and haplic Cambisol (FAO 1988). Thus, main differences arise in Spain concerning to Cambisols also when compared to the Atlas (Figure 4.2), since Cambisols formed from silicic materials in Figure 4.3a, are classified as Regosols in the map of Figure 4.1 and in the Atlas. This is not surprising because of the wider

definition of “cambic horizon” (from the Italian “cambiare,” meaning “to change”) which characterize the Cambisols (as it occurs with the Inceptisols in the Soil Taxonomy) as subsurface horizons with evidence of alteration compared with the underlying horizon. They could develop from all types of parent materials, whether acid, such as granite, slates, sandstone, acid or basic schist, phyllites, lutites, volcanic rocks and basic and ultrabasic rocks, or calcareous materials such as limestone and marly limestones. Even, because their similarity with the parent material, some “possible Cambisols” could be classified as Regosols excluding the group Cambisol if the profile do not meet all the requirements (i.e. alteration signs not visible because tillage and longtime use for agriculture). Regosols as the RSG comprising those soils that cannot be included in other groups, therefore, are under “definition by exclusion” criteria. Also, if Regosols, without any characteristic pedogenetic process giving name to diagnostic horizons, are formed on sandy materials, could be classified as Arenosols because their textural class and, in an agronomic sense, the subsequent especial physical, chemical and biological properties. Other explanations for the differences between all these maps are i) in cases where two Soil Taxonomic Units (STUs) coexisted in a polygon some expert judgment was applied to decide to unite them into the most abundant/main pedogenetic process giving the name to the Reference Soil Group (RSG) or ii) after discussions on the correctness of translation of the codes from the FAO legend to the version of WRB that existed at the time (explained in the personal communication with ESDAC in the methodology Chapter). In fact, the Cambisols in the northern Spain change to Umbrisols and most of the rest change to Calcisols. Leptosols (soils with limited rooting) also differ between rendzic or umbric, depending on calcareous or acidic parent material. umbric Leptosols in the North Spain could also been included in Umbrisols.

According to simplified concepts based in pedogenetic factors Umbrisols, Arenosols, Cambisols and Regosols are relatively young soils or soils with little (Cambisols) or no profile development. It is worthy to mention that Umbrisols in the North Spain cover wide range of pH, 4.0–6.5, and SOM content, 2–33 %, generally very low base saturation, and a high content in exchangeable Al and sandy-loam texture. In the soils of Galicia (Northwest of Spain) with high content in SOM but very low content of available Ca and Mg, the large amount of Al provokes the immobilization of N and P, diminishing the fertility of these soils.

It is worthy to mention that each RSG in the WRB is provided with a wide list of possible prefix and suffix qualifiers, of which the user can build the first and second level units but the broad principles governing WRB differentiation classes at the highest categorical level, are differentiated according to the primary pedogenetic process that has produced the elements or characteristic properties of soils (per example, Calcisol for calcic Cambisol as the calcic properties were deemed to overrule the cambic ones; Umbrisol for umbric Cambisol. When considered that soil parent materials are of dominant importance in conferring elements or characteristic properties to soil, for example gypsum, gypsic Calcisol could also be Gypsisol as in Ebro valley, Alicante and Murcia region in Spain (Figure 4.1, in lemon color).

While we provide the example of Spain to explain these differences, each nation has solved its own problem. But the main problem, which is to be able to compare the soils of two or more countries, necessitates a clear classification. Whether ESDAC’s own classifications of each country or simply the two different systems applied. The World Reference Base (WRB) for Soil Resources 2006, first updated in 2007 (IUSS Working Group) aims to solve this problem because it “is not meant to substitute for national classification systems but rather to serve as a common denominator for communication at an international level”. In this sense, the Atlas classification is clearer and more comparable among the studied countries, mainly for the Mediterranean ones.

Other represented group in these countries are Luvisols and Vertisols. Most of them, in the Mediterranean climate, are cultivated. In facts Vertisols are frequently cultivated with permanent

crops. Luvisols and Vertisols are soils with a clay-enriched subsoil. The neutral to alkaline pH have important implications for the fertility, their use, development, and management compared to Acrisols. In this way, the content and type of clay particles determine the characteristic high cation exchange capacity as a reserve of potential nutrients (fertility potential) and the percentage of basifier cations (base saturation) as a reserve of available nutrients (current fertility). The Vertisol group is defined by the amount and composition of the clay fraction, with high capacity to stock organic matter, interchange nutrients and retention of water. Vertisols are characterized by vertic properties, typified by intense cracking, shrinkage and retraction processes that are mostly related to changes in humidity and caused by the abundance of expansive clay minerals (smectite). The wide separation between smectic clay sheets allows for the entry of water between sheets, in turn causing a volume change while facilitating soil structuration, resulting in a high cation exchange capacity, high thermodynamic stability, and high iron content. Luvisols and Vertisols are very good agricultural soils that have been fundamental for the increase in human population.

Figure 4.1. Soil type map of Into-DIALOGUE countries (Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, and Latvia), except Turkey due to data availability. First level classification according to the World Reference Base for Soil Resources (WRB). Source: ESDAC and Panagos (2006).

Figure 4.2. Soil type map of Eurasia, according to the World Reference Base for Soil Resources (WRB). Source: extracted and modified from the Soil Atlas of Europe (European Commission, 2005).

Figure 4.3. Soil type explanation support maps (Spain’s example). Figure 4.3a. Most abundant soil types in Spain, according to the FAO/UNESCO Classification (1988 version). Figure 4.3b. Distribution of rock materials in Spain: brown signifies silicic Spain (acid materials, as granites, schists, and slates); green calcaric Spain (limes and calcaric rocks); and yellow, sedimentary Spain (clays and other sediments). Source: J. F. Gallardo (2016).

4.2 Soil texture

Figures 4.4 and 4.5 both show the soil texture of Europe according to the USDA (United States Department of Agriculture) texture class definition. Since only Figure 4.5 includes Turkey, this is the one used for the comparison. Nonetheless, both maps show very similar results.

Spain, Italy, and Turkey, which are situated in a similar latitude, show a great amount of land classified as clay loam. Spain, the north of Italy, and both the east and south-west of Turkey also show the presence of loam soils. Clay and silty clay loam are also prevalent in Italy and Turkey. Loam also constitutes a big part of the Czech Republic, the south of Poland, Latvia, and Lithuania. On the other hand, sandy loam makes up the majority of Poland, and large areas of Lithuania and Latvia.

In relation to soil health, soil texture is the soil property with the greatest influence on the microbial population. This is important, since microbial population density and functional diversity are the most important indicator of soil quality and soil health. It is less favourable for coarse particles size such as the sandy textured soils. Another very important soil parameter is the soil organic matter content (SOM), which is addressed in the following Chapter 4.3.

Figure 4.4. Soil texture map of Europe texture class definitions from USDA (United States Department of Agriculture). Source: extracted from ESDAC (Ballabio et al., 2016).

Figure 4.5. Soil texture map of Into-DIALOGUE countries. Derived layer showing predominant soil texture to 1 meter depth. Texture class definitions from USDA (United States Department of Agriculture). Resolution of 250m. Source: Poggio et al. (2021), link: <https://soilgrids.org>.

4.3 Soil organic carbon

Figure 4.6 shows the topsoil carbon content in Into-DIALOGUE countries. It ranges from less than 15 g C kg⁻¹ to 125 g C kg⁻¹. If we could see the farther northern regions of Eurasia, higher values could be found. Regardless, it is especially noticeable that the more northern countries such as Lithuania and Latvia tend to contain more SOC (Soil Organic Carbon), mostly Latvia.

Poland and the Czech Republic are quite heterogeneous, with most of its land ranging 21 to 36 g C kg⁻¹. Meanwhile, Spain, Italy, and Turkey vary a lot more. In Spain and Turkey, there are many areas with low SOC, ranging from less than 15 g C kg⁻¹ to 21 g C kg⁻¹.

Figure 4.6. Topsoil organic carbon map of Into-DIALOGUE countries. Derived layer estimating carbon content of soils to a depth of 30 centimetres. Carbon content is expressed in grams of carbon per kilogram of soil (g C kg⁻¹). Resolution of 250m. Source: Poggio et al. (2021), link: <https://soilgrids.org>.

4.4 Land use/cover of Europe

Figure 4.7 presents the land use/cover of the project's countries. Starting by Spain, its northern regions, especially along the coast, are predominantly characterized by forests and shrubs. This forested region extends to certain central parts of the country and through the east coast. Scattered patches of grasslands can be predominantly observed across the country, with most grassland areas present in the north-west (mainly in Galicia and Asturias). While agricultural lands are dispersed throughout the country, notable concentration can be discerned in the Castilla la Mancha and Castilla and León regions. The amount of permanent crop trees in Spain, surpasses every other Into-DIALOGUE country. These are mainly found in the eastern and southern regions. Settlements are mainly found in the coast, with the exception of Madrid, which is set in the centre, connecting the country.

Forests and shrubs are mainly distributed throughout the northern regions of Italy, particularly in the Alps, and extending down the Apennine Mountain range which runs along the length of the country. The southern tip and the island of Sicily also show a notable presence of forests and shrubs. Agricultural activities, as indicated by the map, seem to be widespread across the central regions of the country, especially in the Po Valley. Throughout the country, but mainly in the middle east, there is a dominant presence of permanent crop trees. It is worth highlighting the extensive cultivation of rice in the Lombardy, Piedmont, and Veneto regions.

The Czech Republic displays a mix of land uses. Forests seem to be more dominant towards the borders surrounding the Czech Republic. This is mainly caused by the mountain relief, which surrounds practically all the country and by resettlement of 2,9 millions of German inhabitants from so-called Sudetenland – which basically copy the forest regions. Grasslands and agricultural plots are dispersed throughout the country but show a denser presence in central regions.

In Poland, forests and shrubs are predominantly found in the north and northeastern parts, potentially including areas of the ancient Pomerania and Masuria forests. The central regions of Poland demonstrate a vast expanse of agricultural land, which can be associated with the country's extensive plains that are propitious for farming.

Forests cover significant portions of Lithuania, especially towards the eastern and southeastern borders. The central and western parts, on the other hand, seem to have more agricultural and grassland areas, representing the fertile plains of the region.

Latvia has a widespread forest cover, with forests appearing dominantly in the western, central, and eastern parts on sandy parent material. Agricultural lands and grasslands are interspersed among these forested areas, with the main agricultural regions focused on the south of the country.

While Turkey is the biggest country included in Into-DIALOGUE by far, it also shows immense diversity in its land use/cover distribution. Forests and shrubs are heavily present across the country. In particular, the northern coast of Turkey (adjacent to the Black Sea) and certain parts of the west exhibit dense forest cover, potentially representing the Black Sea and Aegean forests. The central region, particularly the Anatolian plateau, is characterized by vast agricultural lands and grasslands, which could be due to its continental climate and extensive plains. The southeastern part displays a mix of forests, grasslands, and agricultural plots. Settlements and other urban regions are distributed sporadically across the country, reflecting Turkey's diverse demographic distribution.

Figure 4.7. Land use/cover map of Into-DIALOGUE countries (Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, and Turkey). Base map from CORINE (Coordination of information on the environment) with 44 classes, reclassified into 9 simplified classes for 2018. Satellite data from Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 for gap filling. The minimum mapping unit of 25 hectares and the minimum width of linear elements of 100 meters. Source: Generated using European Union's Copernicus Land Monitoring Service information; <https://doi.org/10.2909/960998c1-1870-4e82-8051-6485205ebbac>

4.5 Land use/cover and crop selection in Europe

Figure 4.8 combines the land use/cover map from CORINE, with the crop selection data from SAR-LUCAS. This provides a fairly accurate representation of the European agrarian landscape (for INTO-DIAOGUE countries, except Turkey). Starting by Spain, it exhibits a rich mixture of crop selections across its terrain. The central plateau is characterized by a mix of cereals, mainly wheat. This is scattered with grasslands, sunflower, other cereals, forest and shrubs, and permanent tree crops depending on the area. The southern parts, particularly Andalusia, have a noticeable presence of permanent crop trees, likely olive groves or fruit orchards. The eastern coastline, especially in regions like Valencia, exhibits patches of rice cultivation and citrus trees.

Italy also portrays a varied crop selection across the country. In the northern regions, including Lombardy and Emilia-Romagna, Figure 4.8 shows a clear “corn belt”, where maize cultivation is prominent. Moving southwards towards Tuscany and Lazio, there's a mix of wheat, other cereals, and significant patches of permanent crop trees such as vineyards or olive orchards. The southern tip, including regions like Calabria, are scattered with some root crops. The islands of Sicily and Sardinia reflect a mix of cereals, permanent crop trees, and grasslands.

The Czech Republic, situated in the heart of Europe, predominantly displays a mix of wheat, other cereals, and grasslands throughout its territory. There's also a relevant presence of rapeseed, coupled with protein crops, among the cereal fields.

Poland's landscape, as depicted, majorly revolve around a mix of wheat, maize, and other cereals, especially in its central regions. A large part of the heavily cultivated land has close connections to rivers, such as the Odra in the South.

Both Lithuania and Latvia, situated in the Baltic region, display a mix of wheat, other cereals, and grasslands. This is mainly the case for Lithuania, since Latvia devotes less land to agriculture.

Figure 4.8. Land use/cover and crop selection map of Into-DIALOGUE countries (Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, and Turkey). Base maps from CORINE (Coordination of Information on the Environment) and SAR/LUCAS. The CORINE (2018) map is composed of 44 classes, reclassified into 9 simplified classes; satellite data from Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 for gap filling; and minimum mapping units of 25 hectares and minimum width of linear elements of 100 meters. The crop selection map is based on Eurostat LUCAS in-situ data and Sentinel-1 (S1) Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) observations, with a 10-meter resolution and 80.3% accuracy. It does not include data for Turkey. The original 23 classes are reclassified into 8 simplified classes. Sources: European Union's Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (2018; based on Figure 4.7) and d'Andrimont et al. (2021).

4.6 Land use/cover and crop's impact on soil health

The criterium selected to create Figure 4.9 was the impact on soil properties by particular crops grown. It is widely known that different crops have various impacts on soil physical, chemical (Zuber et al., 2015; Stone and Schlegel, 2010) and biological properties (Carter et al., 2009). It was necessary to separate crops into four categories based on the impact. The criteria were: interrow space (i.e., Weil, 1982) and length of growing season (Zuazo and Pleguezuelo, 2009), which is crucial within erosion predisposition, demand of chemicalization (Pal et al., 2010), presence of associative beneficial organisms (*Rhizobia* etc.) and usual technology using included organic fertilizing, irrigation, land processing etc. The division was assessed subjectively, however based on objective data from variable sources (Podmanicky et al., 2011; Bünemann et al., 2018). This fact is a bottleneck after all. The main constraint of this statement is that data chosen for creating this map essentially ignored the place of particular crops within crop rotation and particular technology applied. For a demonstration of this problem, it should be mentioned that even high risky crops (for example corn) can be grown using technologies like strip-till, collaterally with organic fertilizing etc. and therefore their impact on soil would not be negative after all. This map aims to simplify the issue and provide a general overview. The crops were divided as follows:

Mild impact crops – narrow interrow space, relatively long growing season (autumn or early spring sowing), medium level of chemicalization, occasionally using organic fertilizers. The main crops are common wheat, durum wheat, oats, barley, triticale, rye and other C3 cereals.

Risky crops, which under non optimal circumstances cause soil depletion – wide interrow space, short growing season with frequent use of organic fertilizers (maize, sunflower, potatoes, and sugar beets) or plants with high level of chemicalization and lack of organic fertilizing (turnip rape and rapeseed).

Beneficial impact crops – narrow interrow space, with exceptions long growing seasons (even several years), almost no demand for pesticides and mineral fertilizers, frequent presence of beneficial microorganisms and direct influence on organic fertilizers production with subsequent offer. The main crops are soya, dry pulses, and other fodder crops (alfalfa, red clover, non-perennial grasses).

Variable impact crops are characterized by “enrichment” of crop rotation. Among these crops we decided to classify vegetables and other root crops. Their impact on soil is to diversify agroecological characteristics.

Figure 4.9. Land use/cover and crop's impact on soil health map of Into-DIALOGUE countries (Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, and Turkey). Base maps from CORINE (Coordination of information on the environment) and SAR/LUCAS. The CORINE (2018) map is composed of 44 classes, reclassified into 9 simplified classes; satellite data from Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 for gap filling; and minimum mapping units of 25 hectares and minimum width of linear elements of 100 meters. The crop selection map is based on Eurostat LUCAS in-situ data and Sentinel-1 (S1) Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) observations, with a 10-meter resolution and 80.3% accuracy. It does not include data for Turkey. The original 23 classes are reclassified into 4 simplified classes, based on literature and expert knowledge. Sources: European Union's Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (2018; based on Figure 4.7) and d'Andrimont et al. (2021)

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